

EOOSC DIH
DIGITAL INNOVATION HUB

2021 PUBLICATION

BUSINESS PILOT SUCCESS STORIES

Digitizing Industry through
the European Open Science Cloud

eosc-dih.eu

The EOSC DIH is a publication of the EOSC DIH project, edited to showcase major results and achievements of the project, collaborations ongoing with other initiatives and updates from the communities. The publication also provides an overview of the latest highlights from the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) landscape.

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Services for Business

Digitising Industry through the European Open Science Cloud

The EOSC Digital Innovation Hub (DIH) is the mechanism for private companies to collaborate with public sector institutions within the European Open Science Cloud in order to access technical services, research data, and human capital. The EOSC DIH kick-started with six business pilots that were pre-selected during the project's preparation phase. Over the last 18 months, these pilots have worked to mature their service offering and achieved incredible success. The EOSC DIH is open for more collaborations and has already started to onboard new pilots. If you are looking for new opportunities to advance your business, we invite you to contact us now to identify how you can become part of the European Open Science Cloud.

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SY HOLSINGER
EGI Foundation
EOSC DIH Coordinator

I am extremely proud of the number of pilots and individual companies we supported, the results achieved by them, and the dedication shown by the EOSC DIH team. The success of these business pilots demonstrates the tangible value that the EOSC DIH can bring to the private sector industry, especially start-ups and SMEs. These kinds of joint ventures prove that we are stronger by working together, leveraging the services, skills and knowledge available across the public sector, coupling with the innovation and business acumen of the private sector to directly stimulate economic growth and impact. We are excited to build on these success stories and the momentum generated to drive industry engagement into the future of the European Open Science Cloud

MARCIN PLOCIENNIK
PSNC
EOSC DIH Business Pilot Manager

It has been a great pleasure to work closely with innovative SME's that are part of the EOSC DIH Community. Many new innovative services have been developed, some integrated with the EOSC Marketplace, which we believe will enrich the overall offer for research communities. An example of appreciation of the effort was shown by having won two prizes during EOSC related events: for best demonstration and for best poster.

We would like to thank all of the pilots that not only delivered new services, but also through their feedback, helped shape and mature the DIH itself with their pragmatic business-oriented views and requirements.

Through this experience, and lessons learned, we are well-positioned to support even better future pilots

CyberHAB

Using data cloud services to manage harmful algae blooms

BACKGROUND

Harmful Algal Blooms (HABs) happen when toxic microalgae proliferate beyond control and take over rivers, lakes or ponds with costly environmental and socioeconomic impacts, for example: on fisheries, or on the availability of drinking water. At sea, this phenomenon causes red tides. Managing algal blooms is a challenge for local governments, environmental agencies and the people that depend on healthy water bodies for their livelihood. Despite the investment in waste management and monitoring systems, current methods and processes are still far from ideal. Ecohydros believes that new technologies and big data can pave the way for better and more efficient ways to manage harmful algal blooms.

ACHIEVEMENTS

As part of their collaboration with EOSC-hub, Ecohydros developed CyberHAB - a platform to process and analyse ecological data related to algal blooms. The CyberHAB prototype is a platform with a Jupyter Notebooks interface that integrates software components transparently and provides direct access to cloud computing resources. This platform can be used to extract information from monitoring data, converting hundreds of variables and parameters into visualizations to support decision-making.

WHICH EOSC-HUB SERVICES DID YOU USE?

CyberHAB uses Notebooks as an interface and processes analysis with the EGI Cloud Compute service. The user is able to access different data sources by selecting ranges of dates and locations. The data is stored in a cloud storage solution (Onedata, Datahub) and whenever they need to launch a new model or simulation it is deployed using PaaS Orchestrator.

WHAT MAKES YOUR PRODUCT STAND OUT? WHAT IS YOUR VALUE PROPOSITION?

CyberHAB is the first cyberinfrastructure of its kind – a versatile platform powered by cloud computing able to combine large volumes of data for the management of harmful algal blooms. Users can interact with CyberHAB in different ways, via Web or mobile interfaces. With a registered free account, users can try basic functionalities with their own data. Subscriptions give access to the full range of tools, including models to forecast scenarios or methods to generate additional data for a given case.

WHAT WAS THE VALUE OF WORKING WITHIN THE EOSC-HUB PROJECT?

CyberHAB manipulates data covering hundreds of variables that need to be treated, processed and analysed before being used in visualizations. The predictive models also require calibration. The computing demands are beyond what a standard company or a standard computer center can provide. EOSC-hub gave us a chance to overcome this barrier.

Services:
EGI Cloud Compute, PaaS Orchestrator,
Jupyter Notebooks

Output:
A working prototype of CyberHAB

Business Partners:

EOSC Providers:

VAMOS

Analysing sports performance through a cloud hosted platform

BACKGROUND

Top-level athletes often record training sessions for review and analysis, looking for weak spots to address with specific training. Continuous improvement in sports also implies having a way to keep track of an athlete's performance over time. As of today, that is chiefly done by hand and depends on the athlete's and the coach's interpretation of the training videos. The amount of data can be huge, since every athlete or every player of a team can be recorded in a training session at least at 50 frames per second, and from every frame many patterns can be identified and tracked. And to optimize the analysis, performance must be monitored during the entire season. The idea for VAMOS comes from this need for a smart video processing tool able to extract KPIs in a data-driven and automated way.

ACHIEVEMENTS

As a EOSC-hub business pilot, Moxoff developed VAMOS - Video Analysis for Movement Optimization and Statistical analysis – a web-application where each authenticated user can analyze and monitor performance of an athletic gesture. VAMOS is scalable and automatic, i.e. there is no need for human supervision: the final user will upload one video per gesture, together with some additional information and will receive as output a report with advanced statistics on his training sessions, such as consistency, best repetition, quantitative indicators.

WHICH EOSC-HUB SERVICES DID YOU USE?

Moxoff deployed two virtual machines (VMs) using the EGI Cloud Compute service: one for the front-end of VAMOS, the other for the back-end requiring more computational resources. The specs were:

- Back-end VM:
12 vCPU, 22GB RAM, 1 GPU 1080Ti
- Front-end VM:
4 vCPU, 7.3GB RAM, Disk 30GB

WHAT MAKES YOUR PRODUCT STAND OUT? WHAT IS YOUR VALUE PROPOSITION?

VAMOS allows coaches and athletes to save time and increase their efficiency as the data is processed by advanced algorithms and methods (such as functional data analysis) automatically, extracting all the KPIs they need in standard reports.

WHAT WAS THE VALUE OF WORKING WITHIN THE EOSC-HUB PROJECT?

Working within the EOSC-hub project gave Moxoff the possibility to reach a wide audience and a very active network working on mathematical modelling, data science and optimization. The international experience allowed created new opportunities for the future. From the technical point of view, the cloud infrastructure which has been made available increased Moxoff's computational capability, necessary to scale up and to process huge amount of data.

Services:
Cloud Compute

Output:
A working prototype of VAMOS (winner of the best demo prize in the EOSC-Hub Week 2019)

Business Partners:

EOSC Providers:

ACTION Seaport

Smart-port technologies for improved safety and operations

BACKGROUND

With 74% of goods coming to Europe by sea, ports are vital elements of the economic machine. Increased traffic and ship size add pressure on their productivity and can cause congestion and delays, burdening shippers, transport operators, and ultimately consumers with extra costs. As a consequence, a seaport's efficiency, competitiveness, and reputation can decline. Luckily, new digital solutions taking advantage of the Internet of Things, big data analytics and numerical models might not only ease their daily operational activities, but also boost seaport performance in the long-term.

ACHIEVEMENTS

In this context, Bentley Systems designed and implemented ACTION Seaport, an advanced cloud-based and mobile-friendly platform to support decision-making for port authorities. ACTION Seaport helps port authorities and operators to improve maritime situational awareness, provides early-warning notifications for adverse conditions, and delivers piloting and navigation support. ACTION Seaport can also be used by other parties, such as coastguards, search and rescue forces, or maritime offices.

WHICH EOSC-HUB SERVICES DID YOU USE?

The ACTION Seaport pilot used Cloud Computing provided by PSNC for implementation of different tiers (presentation, business and data) with redundancy, using Windows environment. The pilot deployed two Virtual Machines with 20 VCPU and 40 GBytes of memory to perform scalability tests and get perspective for the increasing number of potential customers.

WHAT MAKES YOUR PRODUCT STAND OUT? WHAT IS YOUR VALUE PROPOSITION?

Using an innovative, holistic, accurate, and cost-effective approach, ACTION Seaport improves port efficiency, competitiveness, and safety, particularly their environmental, navigational, and operational/logistical aspects. ACTION Seaport makes it possible to minimize port congestion and optimize berth planning by using continuous and dynamic AIS-based operational port performance indicators (geospatial data analytics) computed in real-time or for user-specified periods.

WHAT WAS THE VALUE OF WORKING WITHIN THE EOSC-HUB PROJECT?

Thanks to the EOSC-hub business pilot, ACTION Seaport assessed the pros and cons of hosting its system on a cloud service.

Services:
Cloud Compute provided by PSNC

Output:
A cloud-deployed ACTION Seaport platform

Business Partners:

EOSC Providers:

Guardomic

Securing online services from botnet attacks

BACKGROUND

Web services owners struggle daily to protect their websites from bot traffic and their users from fraudulent digital ads or cryptocurrency web mining. The problem is not going away: recent years show an increasing number of bot attacks in the global network. For example, considering just online ads, the Association of National Advertisers and White Ops estimates that in 2016, bots were responsible for seven billion dollars of wasted resources. The solution is to “know thy website” via analytics and in-depth statistics that provide insight on the website traffic, and turn those insights into defenses from botnet attacks.

ACHIEVEMENTS

As part of their collaboration with EOSC-hub, Koma Nord and Idego designed and developed Guardomic – a tool suite to protect online services from botnets attacks. Guardomic also allows to analyze and block unwanted traffic (i.e. from specified country, specified ISP, IP range) without decreasing performance for the reader. With Guardomic, consumers can decide between two types of installation: PaaS and on-premise. Both are transparent for the user. Web-site administrators can also choose only to analyze the traffic, or block the hostile bad-bot infiltration. Regardless of choice, the administrator has full access and control and can decide which options to enable and which statistics to see.

WHICH EOSC-HUB SERVICES DID YOU USE?

The team needed a flexible server and storage platform that they could remotely access, configure and manage during the development of Guardomic. As a EOSC-hub pilot, they were able to use the Compute Cloud resources provided by PSNC, namely their OpenStack cloud platform, as a development environment and a production platform for the clients testing the prototype.

WHAT MAKES YOUR PRODUCT STAND OUT? WHAT IS YOUR VALUE PROPOSITION?

Hackers move fast, but Guardomic keeps up with the pace. The development team behind Guardomic is very flexible and can act quickly to add new features according to new market demands. The team is also focused and efficient, which allows Guardomic to be marketed at a competitive price without compromising on quality.

WHAT WAS THE VALUE OF WORKING WITHIN THE EOSC-HUB PROJECT?

Working within EOSC-hub has allowed Koma Nord and Idego to develop and implement Guardomic quicker and more efficiently. As part of the EOSC Digital Innovation Hub, they are also now part of large European consortia of science institutes, companies and other organizations, which brings added opportunities for business and extended collaborations. Koma Nord will also take advantage of the EOSC Marketplace as a platform to promote Guardomic as a solution to mitigate botnet attacks.

Services:
Openstack Compute Cloud platform,
with IaaS resources provided by PSNC

Output:
A fully-functional release of Guardomic
– a solution to secure online services
from botnet attacks

Business Partners:

EOSC Providers:

DS-DRACO

A cloud framework for state-of-the-art Space Weather data

BACKGROUND

Space Weather concerns the phenomena that arise from the changing physical conditions of the Sun and its effects at Earth. It may seem an abstract topic, but events such as Geomagnetic Storms have actual practical and economic consequences at Earth, especially as our economies are increasingly dependent on technology and satellite communications and services. The possible consequences and damages due to Space Weather can be mitigated with appropriate protocols that rely on accurate forecasts. The DRACO project will establish a planetary network of observatories capable of generating high-resolution cosmic ray Space Weather data with an unprecedented level of detail. An advanced cloud infrastructure is essential to manage the distribution and ensure the availability of this Space Weather data. The DS-DRACO pilot, developed by Hidronav as an EOSC-hub business pilot, is the first step to develop such data infrastructure.

ACHIEVEMENTS

The underlying DS-DRACO pilot infrastructure is currently storing and providing access to high-resolution data from and for early adopters. The database currently includes data from the MuTT (Muon ToF Tracker) detector. The TRISTAN detector of the ORCA Antarctic Cosmic Ray Observatory provided by the University of Santiago de Compostela is also confirmed to use this platform for its data distribution. The research-facing web portal www.spaceweatherhub.eu is now online, as a hub of interoperable data for Space Weather modelers and forecasters. Future Space Weather products derived from raw data will be distributed through this platform.

WHICH EOSC-HUB SERVICES DID YOU USE?

Hidronav used the Cloud Compute service, with dedicated resources provided by CESGA, for the back-end of their data management platform. Cloud Compute ensures the scalability they need for a growing global detector network and the high-availability mechanisms such as system redundancies (electrical power, air conditioning) and IT infrastructure redundancies (server redundancy, processors and storage in high-availability cabins, redundant internet service, etc.).

WHAT WAS THE VALUE OF WORKING WITHIN THE EOSC-HUB PROJECT?

Joining forces with EOSC-hub means that DS-DRACO can access the Cloud Computing resources needed to meet increasing processing, storing and high-availability requirements. This ensures that the service can safely be used in applications such as Space Weather extreme event warning and forecasting models.

Services:

EGI Cloud Compute

Output:

An online portal with data for Space Weather modelers and forecasters

Business Partners:

EOSC Providers:

DataFurn

Platform-as-a-Service data analytics for the furniture industry

BACKGROUND

Thanks to the spread of social media and on-line communities, furniture manufacturers now have access to a pool of readily available data on end-users' preferences, opinions about brands and products, as well as to users willing to provide new ideas, assess solutions and co-design new products. Manufacturers can extract a lot of value from contact with their customers, moving away from an outdated mass manufacturing scenario towards a more individualized production. Furniture designers can now take customers' opinions into account in the design of innovative, more customized and trending products that customers demand. In other words, companies will produce better products for more commercial value if they have a broader and clearer view of what their customers are discussing online. However, despite the tremendous data overflow around, the furniture industry lags behind due to several inherent challenges:

- Social media tools monitor the global trends, but they do not provide actionable insights to the domain's SMEs;
- Furniture SMEs have a limited online presence and therefore the current content is biased towards larger brands;
- Trend prediction methods cannot easily distinguish between promotional and genuine content while facing significant difficulties when it comes to image recognition.
- Lack of a formalized digital strategy in the majority of furniture manufacturers.

ACHIEVEMENTS

With EOSC-hub, Suite5 and AIDIMME designed, developed and deployed DataFurn - a furniture analytics platform-as-a-service. DataFurn collects, analyzes and visualizes online content (e.g. from social media platforms, blogs), detects useful product-related content, extracts relevant furniture product-service topics/features, monitors brand influence and customer interactions and forecasts furniture trends for the upcoming seasons.

WHICH EOSC-HUB SERVICES DID YOU USE?

DataFurn used EGI Cloud Compute to deploy its architecture using ten virtual machines, 80 vCPUs and 160 GBs RAM. Until June 2019, the platform consumed approximately 170 thousand virtual CPU hours and about 340 million RAM hours.

WHY DATAFURN STANDS OUT AND WHAT IS ITS VALUE PROPOSAL?

DataFurn stands out in relation to the generic social media analytics platforms by providing intuitive dashboards that have been already created and curated by furniture domain experts. In this way, DataFurn reduces the necessary effort and time to entry (for setting up, understanding and maintaining the relevant reports of interest). Through a pay-as-you-go business model, SMEs can benefit from a dashboard that leverages untapped information, transforms it into actionable knowledge through intuitive and user-friendly (not requiring any technical background) interfaces and acts as a decision support system (e.g. by allowing for different comparisons in time and in content, better understanding how the discussions and weak signals from other neighbouring domains influence the furniture domain).

WHAT HAS THE EOSC-HUB PROJECT GIVEN TO DATAFURN?

EOSC-hub has provided to DataFurn the necessary infrastructures in order to quickly and efficiently test and deploy its various platform releases. Through the computing power of the EOSC-hub services, DataFurn had the opportunity to experiment on different resource-intensive algorithms for analyzing and indexing the related content that has been curated for manufacturing SMEs.

NEXT STEPS FOR DATAFURN AND FUTURE PLANS

Fifteen companies are currently in the process of testing the DataFurn platform. Each company has received a personalized email to access the platform.

The AIDIMME market experts have prepared a dedicated dashboard to present to the companies the numerous benefits that the DataFurn platform offers them. Future plans also include to attract more companies in the sector, and possibly expand to other domains.

Business Partners:

EOSC Providers:

Services:
Cloud Compute

Output:
DataFurn platform prototype, being tested by 15 furniture companies

DCP

Dynamic resource allocation and accounting in a digital marketplace

BACKGROUND

Federated digital research infrastructure initiatives such as EOSC and Compute Canada are struggling to keep up with demand due to an explosion of AI/ML, big data, and heavy research computing. Issues in cross-border resource provisioning and remittance further frustrate these efforts. Meanwhile, commercial cloud is a large expense for enterprises, unaffordable for smaller researchers, and significant constraint on the pace of innovation.

Kings Distributed Systems' mission is to unlock abundant, affordable, and easy to use computing power by recapturing spare capacity in servers and devices on university campuses, in data centers, government buildings, and enterprise facilities. Its solution, the Distributed Compute Protocol (DCP), is a web-based computing framework that streamlines edge network setup and workload deployment. DCP dynamically characterizes computing workloads, meters resource consumption, and uses fungible "computing credits" to report on individual user consumption.

EOSC data centers in Italy (Catania) and France (Strasbourg), and CENGN data centers in Canada (Toronto, Ottawa, Waterloo) simultaneously ran the DCP Worker. The DCP Workers executed research computing tasks from an epidemiology researcher, returned the results, and received "computing credits" proportional to the computing resources provided.

ACHIEVEMENTS

A researcher's disease modeling job that would have taken 34 days on a single computer only took 3.9 hrs using DCP on EOSC and CENGN infrastructure. Furthermore, the researcher only needed 5 lines of code to go from running their job on one computer to deploying it across 1000. The simplicity of the tool is a major advantage for researchers.

We were able to collect performance metrics from the Workers and from the DCP Scheduler while under load. These metrics helped identify bottlenecks in the system design. Those bottlenecks have now been addressed and the DCP Scheduler can now handle 150,000 connected nodes, and these new Schedulers can be scaled horizontally to accommodate millions of connected Workers. We are hoping to benchmark the new Worker and Scheduler redesign on EOSC infrastructure to see how it compares to previous performance metrics.

HOW THEY USED EOSC-HUB SERVICES

We provided a DCP Worker Debian package that was deployed at two locations: 8 CPU cores at Catalonia, Italy,

and 8 CPU cores in Strasbourg, France. EOSC staff deployed the workers, configured the "compute credit" payment accounts, and monitored credit balances and resource utilization. Feedback on performance and ease-of-use was provided throughout. DCP looks forward to testing the next iteration of the platform with EOSC staff and infrastructure.

THE VALUE PROPOSAL

The Distributed Compute Protocol streamlines massive and cheap computing. DCP eliminates the complexity of configuring environments, version control, dependency management, resource allocation, and accounting. Clients can leverage DCP to lower their cloud computing spend and to accelerate prototyping and discovery.

HOW EOSC-HUB HELPED

EOSC-HUB helped in both direct and indirect ways. Directly, EOSC-HUB provided a testbed and IT support to deploy and benchmark our solution. Performance metrics and user feedback from these tests played a central role in helping us redesign certain components of our software solution, leading to 100x improvement in performance. Indirectly, our work with EOSC-HUB provided a positive credibility signal, allowing us to attract paid pilots and investment. We are very grateful to EOSC-HUB, and certainly hope to keep working with them.

EXPLOITATION AND COMMERCIALIZATION PLANS/STRATEGY AND FUTURE PLANS

Our near-term consists of the intermediate objectives described in Phases I and II. Phase I principally consists in releasing the Public DCP Network MVP, collecting user uptake, churn, and revenue metrics, and executing three high-touch enterprise projects on Private DCP Networks to open key verticals (medical, smart manufacturing, and smart logistics). Phase II will have been achieved when we can claim USD \$8.0M in annual recurring revenue from a combination of Private DCP Network (license fees) and Public DCP Network (brokerage fees) activity. The main effort will shift from the core function to that of the toolchains function towards the end of Phase I. Our addressable market will increase as we expand—and mobilize our community to expand—our DCP toolchains, attracting even more clients to the DCP network (such as matlab-DCP and blender-DCP interfaces).

Simple and powerful Compute API


```
let job = compute.for(inputSet, workFn);  
let resultSet = await job.exec();
```

Services:
Compute

Output:
Dynamic computing resource allocation
and credit-based accounting in a digital
marketplace

Business Partners:

EOSC Providers:

Kampal

Artificial Intelligence for rare disease diagnosis

BACKGROUND

The Spanish Foundation for the Study and Treatment of Gaucher Disease and other Lysosomal Diseases (FEETEG) promotes the scientific research of Gaucher disease and its treatment methods. The Foundation is interested in predicting the probability of development of diseases such as neoplasms or Parkinson's disease in patients of Gaucher disease (correlations between diseases). For this purpose, Kampal Data Solutions was contacted by FEETEG to develop an advanced analytical model based on Artificial Intelligence with the information available in the Gaucher Spanish Disease Registry.

ACHIEVEMENTS

Kampal Data Solutions has developed a machine learning model able to cope with big data samples by using the cloud infrastructure provided by EOSC DIH. The case study was based on a medical data set provided by the FEETEG containing information of patients with Gaucher's disease. In addition, extra data was generated following what the current literature considers normal values. This way allowed the company to obtain a big data sample that loosely resembles the natural proportion of patients with Gaucher Disease. To be able to handle the problem size increment the parallelization of the code was required, benefiting from cloud computing.

HOW THEY USED EOSC-HUB SERVICES

The pilot required extra computational resources to cope with the problem size (1 million samples). For that, Kampal Data Solutions got benefit from the EOSC DIH cloud infrastructure where 16 VCPUs with 32GB of RAM were used. To speed up the process and benefit from all the cores, the code was parallelized. This way, different operations can be done simultaneously on each core using only a fraction on the sequential computational time. The parallelization of the code was greatly simplified by using the R packages parallel and dplyr.

THE VALUE PROPOSAL

Although the obtained results do not have medical value, this proof of concept shows that the chosen model is scalable and could be efficiently applied to other conditions or illnesses where more data is available. The challenge now will be to identify the business opportunities to exploit the model.

HOW EOSC-HUB HELPED

EOSC-hub has provided Kampal Data Solutions with powerful cloud infrastructure to support the scaled up analytics required for validating the proof of concept. Using the computing power of the EOSC-hub services, Kampal Data Solutions could experiment and test its new models for the disease prediction.

The technical support provided from the EOSC DIH team helped Kampal Data Solutions to access and manage the Cloud and provide the company with a better understanding of the EOSC computing infrastructure, meanwhile the visibility service enhanced the exposure of the pilot through different European communities.

EXPLOITATION AND COMMERCIALIZATION PLANS/STRATEGY AND FUTURE PLANS

The validated model is expected to be reused to be adapted and applied to similar diseases. Kampal will open new contacts with other health associations.

Services:
Compute

Output:
A validated Machine Learning model for the Gaucher diagnosis

Business Partners:

EOSC Providers:

BI Insight

Business Intelligence, Artificial Intelligence and Big Data technologies

BACKGROUND

BI Insight S.A. is a Polish company operating in the market since 2006. It specializes in solutions combining Business Intelligence, Artificial Intelligence and Big Data technologies as well as best practices in data management. BI Insight has many years of experience in natural language processing (NLP), closely cooperates in the field with leading academic centers and industry experts and is one of the leaders of this type of solution on the Polish market.

BI Insight has created a system enabling users to access the knowledge contained in artifacts: presentations, text documents, sheets and others. The system utilizes Natural Language Processing and Machine Learning algorithms in creating recommendations, document classification, information retrieval (both from text and images embedded in documents), as well as building intelligent summaries.

The bi ECM system won the first prize in the GOVTECH 2019 competition and became a finalist of the IT Future Awards 2019 competition and has been successfully implemented at the Ministry of Development and is used there by about 150 users.

ACHIEVEMENTS

To meet the challenge of improving work in the area of sharing knowledge and information collected in the organization, we designed and implemented a solution that facilitates access to unlimited resources of knowledge accumulated in the form of unstructured documents, stored in local resources and private and public clouds. A user-friendly search engine using artificial intelligence mechanisms allows to accelerate the process of obtaining information and optimize work in the organization, increasing personal productivity and efficiency of information circulation processes. The use of these features in scientific and academic environments can significantly contribute to accelerating the development of science, innovation, and discovery.

HOW THEY USED EOSC-HUB SERVICES

DoRIS instance deployed to IFCA Scientific Cloud Infrastructure <https://ifca.unican.es/en-us>

Resources consumed: 1 VM instance: 16 vCPUs, 24GB RAM, 1TB storage

THE VALUE PROPOSAL

The DoRIS system facilitates access to unlimited resources of knowledge accumulated in the form of unstructured documents, stored in local resources and private and public clouds. A user-friendly search engine using artificial intelligence mechanisms allows to accelerate the process of obtaining information and optimize work in the organization, increasing personal productivity and efficiency of information circulation processes.

HOW EOSC-HUB HELPED

Thanks to the cooperation with the EOSC-hub, BI Insight took advantage of the additional infrastructure for testing the DoRIS system. In addition, we see an opportunity to get closer to the international scientific community through participation in events organized by the EOSC. Another advantage is the possibility of using the EOSC Marketplace as a platform for presenting the DoRIS demo.

EXPLOITATION AND COMMERCIALIZATION PLANS/STRATEGY AND FUTURE PLANS

We plan to further develop the system with new functionalities based on market needs verification. We have also started a project to develop a prototype of an innovative platform to support the processes of semantic search and inference based on a document model integrating the text and graphic layers. Due to its versatility and ease of use, the solution can be used by a wide range of business users. The main target groups are: public administration, legislative and regulatory institutions, courts and law firms, academic and research centers, historical and literary institutes, document archives and repositories, press and publishing agencies, as well as health care and clinical research centers.

Services:
 Compute, Storage, DEEP platform

Output:
 A cloud-deployed DoRIS system
 enabling testing by interested users or
 companies

Business Partners:

EOSC Providers:

KNOWCO4EOSC

Knowco collabwith platform integrated with the EOSC

BACKGROUND

Collabwith Marketplace is a pilot of EOSC DIH, where scientifics can connect with industry, SMEs and startups to create impact with their scientific knowledge and research results. The Collabwith Marketplace includes a marketplace for collaboration opportunities and knowledge sharing and technology for an effective knowledge transfer and collaboration efficiency such as smart legal contracts to reduce bureaucracy and protect data and protect “knowledge sharing” activities with NDAs with specific clauses for IP, ethics and competition protection. Inside the Collabwith Marketplace scientifics find challenges and technology (TRL3-9) from industry, SMEs and startups, services from industry, products from industry ready to test, open questions from scientifics where they seek other technology and research results from scientifics and funding calls. The pilot consists of the integration of the following applications to enhance the Collabwith marketplace impact within the EOSC community:

1. EOSC SSO (Single Sign On) API Integration to make it possible to sign up and log into the Collabwith Platform.
2. Explore the Integration with the EOSC Marketplace.

ACHIEVEMENTS

Expand the EOSC DIH network with Collabwith network and members. The Collabwith Marketplace is created for collaboration and increased connections between EOSC networks, IT providers, EOSC services providers and EOSC scientifics. The Collabwith Marketplace has already integrated the Check-in SSO with Edugain to facilitate the connectivity between the scientifics between EOSC Marketplace and Collabwith Marketplace. For instance, the pilot has been achieved the following technical integrations:

- Visibility of EGI login button on Login and Sign up page of Collabwith Platform
- Availability of Single Sign On for Collabwith Platform Users
- Availability of Single Sign On for EGI user community
- Hyperlinks to EOSC Marketplace from Collabwith Platform
-

The goal was to increase the quality and success rate of the industry-academia collaboration and reduce the timeline for finding academics, start-ups, SMEs, corporate knowledge and innovation professionals by providing a matchmaking AI and machine learning algorithm as part of the Collabwith marketplace.

HOW THEY USED EOSC-HUB SERVICES

The pilot results will be implemented directly on the Collabwith platform. The pilot results and the EOSC DIH services helped to increase the impact and the performance of the Collabwith platform and services. Collabwith was added as a Service Provider for AAI and the EGI SSO (Single Sign On) has been integrated using the OAuth 2.0 protocol. The AAI system was tested and evaluated on the existing testing and staging environments. Collabwith has used the consulting services from EOSC-DIH to be able to implement and integrate the SSO in the login of the Collabwith platform.

THE VALUE PROPOSAL

This pilot helps to understand and validate the business needs and challenges with the past and present research. The Marketplace inside the Collabwith includes the challenges from other open innovation platforms and the business needs from the startups, SMEs and companies who are members of the Collabwith platform, and those challenges and needs will be matched with the EOSC DIH participants to enhance the collaboration and the time to market of innovative solutions.

Collabwith is a full digital platform helping the academia to work on a digital environment and accept digitalization for collaboration, that has proven being vital, especially during time of crisis.

HOW EOSC-HUB HELPED

EOSC DIH HUB helped to facilitate access to academics to the platform via the integration of the EGI SSO where every European academic can use their university emails and passwords to easily join the Collabwith marketplace. EOSC-HUB followed up the contact with EOSC Marketplace, and the EOSC DIH HUB helped actively navigate the documentation, ticketing system and processes at EGI to make it possible faster and efficiently. Additionally, EOSC DIH HUB shared regularly with us the funding opportunities that Collabwith Marketplace shared to the community providing even greater value.

EXPLOITATION AND COMMERCIALIZATION PLANS/STRATEGY AND FUTURE PLANS

Collabwith will increase its visibility in the scientific and academic thanks to the participation as a pilot of the EOSC DIH and with the integration of the Collabwith Marketplace inside the EOSC Marketplace. Collabwith will increase the number of scientifics and academics into the Collabwith platform, and EOSC Marketplace will increase the number of services coming from the

Collabwith members related to academic services. The SSO is increasing the value, authority and trust of the Collabwith Platform because the SSO facilitates the access of the academic community by using their academic authentication details from EduGain into the sign in and log in of Collabwith Platform. The integration of the SSO will increase the number of academics and scientific into the Collabwith Platform.

Services:

Consultancy, EGI Check in

Output:

Single Sign On to Collab with Platform and integration of EOSC Marketplace

Business Partners:

EOSC Providers:

DEIPDASFD

Decentralized Assessment of FAIR datasets

BACKGROUND

Citizen Science has incredible potential. It might bring millions of new talents all over the world to work on the toughest and the most exciting challenges of humanity. However, it is still not widely popular and lacks quality of projects. We have identified the core problem and found an ultimate solution to it. Imagine how many new discoveries we can get in all possible disciplines and domains if we increase the quality of Citizen Science projects by 10X... Sounds impossible, right? But not anymore – with the Decentralized Assessment System built by DEIP Collective Intelligence Protocol, we can not only achieve a higher level of quality, but also make it scalable. This pilot project is aimed to showcase how DAS can tackle this problem and unlock full potential of Citizen Science.

ACHIEVEMENTS

As a business pilot of EOSC DIH, DEIP was able to find great partners for the pilot and implemented a web-based platform for the EU citizen science projects accelerator. The pilot is based on DEIP's own developed deep-tech innovation - Decentralized Assessment System (DAS). DAS is a peer review system that uses an incentive model with reputation rewards and produces a quantifiable metric about the quality and reliability of any data set(s) being assessed. DAS is designed specifically for assessment of assets in expertise-intensive areas, such as scientific research. DAS introduces a comprehensive and robust assessment model:

- it sources the consensus about the quality of data sets among the domain experts through continuous two-level peer-review;
- it ensures fair rewards for contributions and curation efforts;
- it formalizes the result of assessment into explicit metrics/indicators useful for non-experts.

HOW THEY USED EOSC-HUB SERVICES

We use cloud services from EOSC-HUB partners to develop, test and deploy a pilot for our partners. We mostly utilize the hosting capabilities to host a web-based platform and all supporting services, as well as to host an initial set of blockchain nodes.

THE VALUE PROPOSAL

The pilot can not only showcase how we can unlock the potential of Citizen Science, but also show how we can add enormous value to media business and technology

transfer. Media businesses can benefit from the solution by utilizing objective quality indicators produced by DAS. News that reference scientific research might become much more trustworthy and credible. Technology Transfer from another hand can benefit from DAS by sourcing innovation from the wide market of citizen science projects much more effectively.

HOW EOSC-HUB HELPED

EOSC-HUB helped with brokerage for funding and opportunities, commercialization, and business help. We also got coaching on how to better commercialize solutions for scientific research, as well as got connected with more scientific communities and organizations. The scientific research domain is quite different from other business domains and our team strongly believes that EOSC-HUB provided a great competence and connections to help us to find better ways to approach this domain. We also find your technical infrastructure helpful to better design and test the platform with our business partners.

EXPLOITATION AND COMMERCIALIZATION PLANS/STRATEGY AND FUTURE PLANS

The platform will be used in the ongoing call from the ACTION Project accelerator call that starts on March 1st 2021. Furthermore, together with one of our partners we applied for a grant to create a platform for Climate Change Action projects collaboration and assessment. The pilot use case of the DAS will provide a potential step towards implementing a peer review infrastructure. The expected benefit of this pilot is aligned with the EOSC Interest Groups on Researcher Engagement and Use Cases. The DAS will test reputation-based incentives for reviewers, how it affects the quality and objectivity of reviews, and how efficiently it prevents various review gaming techniques. We will continue to work closely with the thematic communities and engage researchers from this community in the testing.

Services:
Storage

Output:
An online platform for the assessment
of the outputs of the citizen science
projects

Business Partners:

EOSC Providers:

Erasmus Play

Accommodation search engine

BACKGROUND

Over 800.000 people participate in the Erasmus+ mobility program. According to the latest survey by the HousErasmus+, almost 60% of Erasmus+ mobility students had serious difficulties finding accommodation. Mainly due to the lack of information and online scams, +30 million € were lost to the latter in the academic year of 2018/2019.

Erasmus Play is an accommodation metasearch engine for students and young professionals across Europe. The goal is to aggregate all available, and most importantly verified accommodations into the metasearch engine, providing the service of searching and booking as easy and safe as possible. This is done by aggregating verified accommodations from regional and national accommodation platforms into the search engine.

As a startup of the University of Zaragoza, collaborating with stakeholders such as Universities, student associations, Erasmus+ organizations, national agencies etc is the key to being able to help students in need with this tool to find accommodation anywhere. Although this pilot surges from the pain of finding accommodation as Erasmus+ students, it is a tool to help all the +1.5 million international students across Europe.

ACHIEVEMENTS

The search engine was launched in September 2020 offering the search and comparison of accommodation only in Spain. As request for its use in other European countries grew, it was habilitated to enable users to search for accommodation in all European cities by mid-December 2020. Over 30 universities are engaged and collaborating to help both their outgoing and incoming students to find accommodation. The search engine offers over 150.000 accommodations in 24 countries.

HOW THEY USED EOSC-HUB SERVICES

EOSC-hub presented Guardomic services, with whom the metasearch engine is undergoing an extensive audit of its defences against cyberattacks. This continuous audit is strengthening the platform to withstand all potential attacks. EOSC-hub network has been leveraged to obtain high-quality consultancy regarding map services and cloud services.

THE VALUE PROPOSAL

A safe place to lay your head is the first thought everybody has when preparing to stay in a different city.

Erasmus Play aims to avoid home searching as a burden for student, young professional and digital nomads' mobility. The centre of this goal is aggregating only verified accommodation as frauds are on the rise online. A secure one-stop site to find all available and verified accommodation anywhere. The end game is to provide a search tool to make your stay as safe and burdenless as possible.

HOW EOSC-HUB HELPED

EOSC-hub connected us with cloud-based organizations to help us find the best services to host the metasearch engine. As networking with higher education institutes is key to the success of helping students across Europe, EOSC-hub launched a newsletter to its network to enhance collaborations. Map services partners of EOSC-hub were engaged in assisting us with developing an interactive map vision for the accommodation search engine. Guardomic services were introduced to secure a stronger defensive set up of the search engine.

A general methodology of the cybersecurity approach was received from EOSC experts. In the final stage security assessment of the erasmusplay.com service was conducted, covering the analysis of the source code of the service (JavaScript), supported with basic security scans of the <https://erasmusplay.com/> website. The obtained results were collected in the technical report.

EXPLOITATION AND COMMERCIALIZATION PLANS/STRATEGY AND FUTURE PLANS

The metasearch engine is moving forward with continuous growth in offering verified accommodation in all European cities. Tons of verified accommodations in major European cities can be found in the metasearch engine. However, to be a reference search engine for student accommodation, there has to be an extensive offer of verified accommodation in smaller cities with low accommodation offers. It is a must to keep on collaborating with Universities and stakeholders with whom we can assist students in their search, going ahead to collaborate with the Erasmus+ Program itself as a safe spot to mitigate this student hurdle they uncovered in their research.

Services:
Consultancy

Output:
Student accommodation metasearch engine across Europe

Business Partners:

EOSC Providers:

Crop loss assessment stress test

BACKGROUND

IBISA's mission is to enable agriculture insurance for agricultural entrepreneurs. We leverage technology and data to build and manage efficient, scalable and transparent parametric insurance products worldwide and in an easy manner.

One of our key values is the innovative solution for loss assessment. For loss assessment IBISA combines the use of EO products with a Crow-Watching platform. The theory behind is that errors in individual assessment caused by partial information or bias tend to be cancelled.

The objective of this pilot project is to backtest this solution to validate it faster and widely and identify points of improvement.

ACHIEVEMENTS

During the duration of the pilot more than 10,000 crop assessments were done using our platform.

We built and tested a more robust NDVI (vegetation index).

HOW THEY USED EOSC-HUB SERVICES

Through the EOSC network we had access to test-field ground measurements of different parameters, and this helped us for our loss assessment platform calibration.

On the business side EOSC helped us identifying follow-on support to develop a reputation token based incentive model for the 'crowd-assessment' component of our loss assessment solution.

THE VALUE PROPOSAL

IBISA assesses losses on a periodic basis and without relying on data gathered on site. IBISA builds index based (parametric) insurance models, which lower the cost of individual assessment. We reduce damage assessment costs by using index-based triggers based on satellite Earth Observation technology instead of locally gathered rainfall data. IBISA also uses a collaborative "crowd-assessment" or "crowd-watching" to enhance accuracy in a scalable and cost-efficient manner. IBISA involves many "watchers" to derive a consensus from all of them, instead of centralizing decisions. This allows assessment based on transparent index and capability of doing periodic assessments.

All of the damage assessment is done through our state-of-the-art watcher platform, which allows for easy visualization of space imaging and various relevant datasets. Strengthening this part of our solution is key for our business.

HOW EOSC-HUB HELPED

EOSC enabled access to ground data that we could use to calibrate our platform. Furthermore, EOSC enhanced our business development since we could further progress with the evolution of the crowd-watching platform incentives model, which is key in our loss assessment solution.

EXPLOITATION AND COMMERCIALIZATION PLANS/STRATEGY AND FUTURE PLANS

IBISA enables local mutual insurers, takaful, insurers and cooperatives to provide transparent and objective protection (weather index insurance) to their customers. Fully digital end to end platform that includes the policy management system and automated remote loss assessment based on Earth Observation satellite data.

IBISA's current target customers are well established local organizations with large customer base (>500.000 farmers). Typically, these organizations provide several services to farmers, but they lack the expertise and the digital capabilities to provide index-based insurance cost-efficiently and at scale. They have the direct link to the farmers but are missing the products and the tools to distribute and manage them.

IBISA is operational on the field since September 2019 and it has evolved from prototype to MVP.

Our current traction is:

- 1 customer in India (DHAN). Currently 3000 farmers onboarded
- 1 customer in Niger (RBM). Currently 8700 breeders signed-up.
- 1 customer in Philippines (CLIMBS). Product launch in May 2021 with 3600 farmers.
- 1 customer in Switzerland (Food Corporation) that is leveraging our Earth Observation tools and Loss Assessment platform.

Over 5 years we will acquire 14 to 16 customers and reach 3 million farmers with our protection products.

Services:
Consultancy

Output:
Satellite-based remote loss assessment
for crops validation

Business Partners:

EOSC Providers:

BIGcoldTRUCKS

Big data analytics for cold chain logistics optimization in refrigerated trucks

BACKGROUND

Odin Solutions (OdinS) is a SME founded in August 2014 and accredited as an innovative ICT company (EIBT) by MINECO and ANCES. OdinS has a strong background in the R&D fields of Internet of Things, Security and Data Analytic. The pilot contributes to the development of the supply chain 4.0, specifically the cold chain, and it is aligned with the interest of OdinS to contribute in the emergence of smart environments.

ACHIEVEMENTS

We managed to provide a solution that shows the following information:

- **Ranking:** Ranks the products according to their demand in 4 different ways: taking into account the product code, the product label, the groupings on the same trips and the number of pallets.
- **Trip Duration:** we find a list of licence plates and duration in hours of each trip; a table with statistics and a boxplot summarising the results.
- **Seasonality:** Shows the intensity of each product's exports to visualize its seasonality.
- **Geographic Representation:** The origin and destination of the orders are shown as well as the frequency with which the routes are carried out to provide a spatial view of how trips are distributed.

We have indexed the data using ElasticSearch and connected our dashboard to it using the elastic search package. This was a great achievement since this made the dashboard fully operative with respect to results' retrieval time. Not only the calculations are automatic but also the indexing of the data.

We have also managed to provide daily and weekly predictions on the demand of each of the products. This is very useful for stock optimisation.

HOW THEY USED EOSC-HUB SERVICES

We used the Deep Hybrid DataCloud for deploying a Jupyter instance in the DEEP CLOUD testbed with a GPU. This served to ease the machine learning models training that were tested for the prediction of the demand of different products.

We are also at this point, trying to make our model available through the API in order to connect our dashboard to this computing environment. Our intention is to create an entry in the marketplace.

We also received support from the Services of Scientific Data Platforms Department of the Poznan Supercomputing and Networking Center in order to fasten

up the descriptive analysis that is shown in our Dashboard. Following their advice we used the elasticsearch solution, that was deployed in one of their machines, for data indexing. We were able to connect our dashboard to their machines by means of ssh tunneling and the computing speed of the results was greatly improved.

THE VALUE PROPOSAL

Nowadays, many businesses are concerned about collecting data and make great efforts by deploying sensors. However, they lack solutions that extract information from such data. The transportation sector is not an exception.

Our solution provides meaningful knowledge for the logistics business, by giving a better understanding of the trips : product's groupings, duration and product demand seasonality and prediction. Our solution helps in the identification of malpractice. If any kind of event is identified, for example product return, they can easily look for reasons and avoid a similar situation in the future.

The Return of the Investment is very fast. Our solution is implemented by connecting their database to our dashboard. They will immediately have access to our services. With such value, worker-hours can be reduced and therefore the small expense on our solution is quickly recovered given the gain in efficiency.

Our solution goes beyond the Business Intelligence paradigm since it is capable of analysing data in-depth given its connection to the state-of-the-art analytic tools, graphs are of the greatest quality and the functionalities can be customised with little addition of code. It is a flexible, agile solution for more than intelligent, wise logistic business.

HOW EOSC-HUB HELPED

EOSC-hub helped by providing access to experts and tools, and also guidance and supervision through the process. All improvements with regards to operability of the dashboard are thanks to the guidance and provided support.

EXPLOITATION AND COMMERCIALIZATION PLANS/STRATEGY AND FUTURE PLANS

We have submitted a project to the H2020 call Building a low-carbon, climate resilient future: Research and innovation in support of the European Green Deal (H2020-LC-GD-2020) within the SubtopicE. [2021] Reducing food losses and waste at every stage of the food chain including consumption, while also avoiding unsustainable packaging (IA).

In this project, we want to use the previous work focusing on the reduction of waste and dynamic pricing. Our purpose is to use the continuous monitoring of truck conditions from their load to their destiny in order to support real-time assessment of quality and for real-time decision-making in cold chains. This will be done by means of AI methodologies that include demand prediction according to product seasonality and baseline consumption and also product grouping in order to propose a more efficient way to transport goods. Such evaluation of the quality of the products according to trip conditions will be used as input of a dynamic pricing system, lowering the prices for the retailer.

In that sense, we will continue exploiting the solution and adding further functionalities so that it is more complete and covers more areas within the logistic business.

Business Partners:

EOSC Providers:

Services:
Consultancy

Output:
A working prototype of BIGcoldTRUCKS dashboard

Enhancing the Scalability of the Axyon platform

BACKGROUND

Axyon AI is an Italian fintech start-up whose current applications are mainly focused on financial time series analysis with Machine Learning algorithms. More specifically, Axyon AI partners with financial institutions (asset managers, hedge funds, trading desks) to improve the performance and risk profiles of investment strategies. The main objective of the pilot is to work with EOSC DIH as a proof of concept of using the EOSC infrastructure and competences to enhance the TRL of the company services.

ACHIEVEMENTS

The key result of the ESAX project was bringing the computational scalability of the Axyon Platform to a new level, almost quadrupling the previous peak of parallelly executed jobs, with no issue in terms of system management load or network utilization. Moreover, the Platform now supports the optimization of large deep neural network models on multi-GPU multi-node HPC clusters, drastically reducing execution times and paving the way to more complex models and next-generation (e.g. exascale) computing capabilities.

HOW THEY USED EOSC-HUB SERVICES

ESAX used the CINECA HPC Tier-0 system Marconi100 (M100), an HPC cluster composed of 980 nodes equipped with 4 Nvidia v100 GPUs per node and an IBM Power9 AC922 at 3.1 GHz processor. Axyon's AI engine is based on the TensorFlow framework, which can natively exploit the Nvidia multi-GPU technology available on the cluster. M100 also enabled the testing of multi-node distributed training thanks to the Horovod framework that supports TensorFlow. For the project, the Axyon Platform consumed approximately 300k core-hours.

THE VALUE PROPOSAL

At the core of the Axyon Platform sits an automatic meta-optimization engine that executes several parallel jobs using a multitude of different Deep Neural Network morphologies, automatic feature engineering and selection, which requires a large amount of computational power (the typical run cycle of one meta-optimization run takes approximately 1 week on a small GPU cluster). With ESAX, the scalability of the Axyon Platform was dramatically improved, enabling the execution of a much greater number of parallel jobs in parallel, while the runtime of each single job was also reduced by parallelising it over multiple GPUs or even multiple nodes. This allows Axyon to expand its offering by training AI

models with exponentially larger datasets, which may for instance include a wider array of financial assets with much higher granularity level and different explanatory variables (e.g. sentiment data).

HOW EOSC-HUB HELPED

The design and computing power of CINECA HPC Tier-0 system Marconi100 made it an ideal infrastructure for the ESAX project, as the Axyon Platform heavily relies on GPU computing through TensorFlow. The high parallelism capacity of M100 allowed running stress tests on the Platform workload management system to assess and improve its performance and scalability, with invaluable insights provided by CINECA consultants.

EXPLOITATION AND COMMERCIALIZATION PLANS/STRATEGY AND FUTURE PLANS

Axyon's objective is to become a market leader by applying a factory approach to the development of AI-powered investment strategies. To achieve this, the company is building an integrated ecosystem of software solutions to support portfolio managers. ESAX is a key piece of this ecosystem and will help Axyon bring scientific rigor and industry-like automation in the development of AI solutions for investment.

Three main steps constitute the path ahead: (i) integrating more data-providers in the Axyon Platform and partnering with alternative and niche data providers, with the result of automatizing the whole data exploration, selection and download process, (ii) expand the product's market coverage in terms of target asset classes coverage, especially in the fixed-income space, but mainly based on any feedback received from customers and trial users, and (iii) improving the risk management support features to allow the creation of customized end-to-end investment strategies for both asset management firms and large corporate trading desks.

Services:
High Performance Computing

Output:
A scalable multi-GPU multi-node machine learning platform for time series data

Business Partners:

EOSC Providers:

MUON

Tomography for large industrial equipment

BACKGROUND

Muon Systems is a small enterprise founded in 2015. The company develops all necessary hardware and software tools for the application of muon tomography or muography in different sectors like heavy industry, borders security or mining and civil engineering. This technique uses muons, a natural radiation generated at the atmosphere and reaching the earth surface. By studying the interaction of muons with matter, it is possible to reconstruct an image like X-ray radiography.

The objective of this pilot project is to validate by simulation the use of muography to reconstruct the complex inner structure of large industrial equipment.

ACHIEVEMENTS

We managed to produce a full set of simulations with geometry variations that are being used to design our muography algorithms to measure the thickness of the refractory in blast furnaces. These simulations are the first step of the expansion of the company to this kind of problem.

HOW THEY USED EOSC-HUB SERVICES

- Extensive use of computational resources to run simulations needed to develop more sophisticated muography reconstruction algorithms.
- Following the funding opportunities raised and shared by the EOSC-HUB organization.

THE VALUE PROPOSAL

The application of muography to blast furnaces is one of the long-term goals of the company. The development of dedicated algorithms to reconstruct the thickness of the refractory will open the possibility to extend this technique to the preventive maintenance of these objects, opening a large market for the company.

HOW EOSC-HUB HELPED

EOSC-HUB has helped by providing computational resources, guidance about funding opportunities and also increasing the visibility of the company.

EXPLOITATION AND COMMERCIALIZATION PLANS/STRATEGY AND FUTURE PLANS

The simulations produced in the context of this pilot are being used to develop algorithms to measure the thickness of the refractory of the blast furnace. The company is seeking to finish the algorithms and propose a feasibility study to the companies with which the company is already working in other muography applications

Services:
High Performance Computing

Output:
A fully-functional muography simulation
of a blast furnace

Business Partners:

EOSC Providers:

EOSC DIH PARTNERS

Advanced
Computing
for Research

INDIGO - DataCloud
Better Software for Better Science

EUDAT Collaborative
Data Infrastructure

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